

Land-use heterogeneity controls biogenic methane fluxes in urban soils

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Abstract: Urban soils can act as both sources and sinks of greenhouse gases, yet fluxes remain poorly constrained across land uses as cities pursue net-zero emissions. We quantified CH₄, CO₂, and H₂O vapor fluxes across major urban land-use types in Toronto using static chamber measurements from marshes, lawns, treed lawns, street trees (mulched and unmulched), and natural and restored urban forests. A pronounced land-use gradient was observed for CH₄ flux. Urban marshes acted as strong CH₄ sources ($202.70 \pm 28.94 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), whereas natural urban forests ($-2.25 \pm 0.66 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and restored urban forests ($-1.27 \pm 0.16 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) functioned as CH₄ sinks. Treed lawns showed net CH₄ uptake ($-1.09 \pm 0.30 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), while lawns ($-0.08 \pm 0.06 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and street trees were near neutral; mulched street trees were small CH₄ sources ($0.29 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). CO₂ and H₂O fluxes varied across land uses. These results indicate that mitigating methane emissions from urban wetlands—where fluxes exceed wetlands—should be prioritized, alongside strategies enhancing CH₄ uptake in urban soils.